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Tax Planning, Earnings Management and Firm Value in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study applies broad approach to analyse the impact of tax planning on firm value in Nigeria. Added to that, the study also investigates whether earnings management plays any moderating role in the relationship between tax planning on firm value. The study uses unbalanced panel data of 53 quoted companies in Nigeria from the period 2013 to 2015. The panel multiple regression designed for the study were estimated using fixed effect analysis technique. The main findings are in two folds. First, the study indicates that the impact of tax planning is positive and statistically insignificant on firm value. Secondly, the study provides evidence which suggests that earnings management insignificantly moderated the relationship between tax planning and firm value. Unlike previous studies which investigated the effect of tax planning on firm value using a single tax factor, this study is novel in applying tax planning to estimate the impact of tax savings on firm value Furthermore, the study also fills knowledge gap in the literature by providing new evidence indicating that earnings management plays significant role in the relationship between tax planning and firm value.

Keywords: tax planning, earnings management, firm value, fixed effect panel analysis, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

The effect of tax planning and earnings management on firms' value has generated a global interest, by valuating firms' using pre-tax earnings and effective tax rate. Managers of corporate organization has the responsibilities of minimizing tax using tax incentives to maximize profit by creating more value for the business owners. Some of the tax planning might be legal such as increase in debt, roll over relief, investment in fixed asset, increase in approved pension plan, donation, deferred taxation while some as artificial transactions, issues of permanent establishment, transfer pricing, hiding under complex electronic transactions, incomplete transaction disclosures are illegal. From the previous study perspective some researchers report on the activity of tax planning was perceived to have a destructive impact on the firm's value. (MacNaughton and Mawani, 1997; Nanik and Ratna, 2015; Martin J. and Harm S. 2013; Inger 2013; Khaoula Amor and Ahmed 2014). They documented that, while tax planning minimized the firm's tax burdens, it exposed the firm to financial difficulties since no account was taken of the firm's non-tax costs, which sent a negative signal to stakeholders. In Nigeria Nwaobia, Kwarbai , and Ogundajo 2016 worked on how tax planning affect the operating capacity of firm value, without taking market reactions into considerations while Ilaboya, Izevbekhai, Ohiokha 2016 worked on review of literature, which only captured analysis of the literature. None of these studies factored current Nigerian situation considering tax agency strategies and stakeholders reaction of tax planning on value of firms to the best of our knowledge. However, as tax agencies are on the pressure of increasing government revenue through taxation, this has created another face for

firm valuation through tax planning. This agencies has increase its drive on tax audit and investigations on Nigeria firms publishing reports on firm's tax planning strategies, by using their statutory tax rate and effective tax rate. This recent process will lead to another valuation of Nigeria firms by stakeholders ranging from government, intending investors, business managers, stock market analyst and business owners. This process by the agencies is the motivating factor of this research trying to find out the effect of tax planning and earnings management practices on the value of consistently trading quoted firms in Nigeria. What is the tax planning reaction to quoted firms? Is it significant? To what extent of significant? Is it positive or negative?

To address these gaps in the tax planning and earnings management on firm value literature, a sample of 53 high trading firms in Nigeria stock exchange from 2013 to 2015 is used. The variables of interest are firm value model (a measure of TobinQ), modified Jones earnings management model (a proxy for of earnings management), tax planning, tax saving, effective tax rate, book tax gap and tax shelter (as tax planing indicators). This study attempts to answer two questions: (1) Does tax planning and earnings management adoption significantly affects firms value in Nigeria? (2) Is the interaction of tax planning and earnings management adoption significantly affects firms value in Nigeria? The empirical investigation employs pooled, panel regression with fixed and random effect panel data regression technique. Our findings, for the most part, align with previous studies. The rest of the paper is structured as Section 2 briefly reviews empirical literature on tax planning. It discusses its effect on tax planning. The research design is described in Section 3, while Section 4 presents and discusses the empirical findings. Section 5 provides a summary of the results, conclusion and recommendations.

2.0 Review of related literature

Tax Planning Policies

Investopedia defined tax planning as the analysis of a financial situation or plan from a tax perspective to ensure tax efficiency, with the elements of the financial plan working together in the most tax-efficient manner possible. It is an important part of a financial plan, as reducing tax liability and maximizing eligibility to contribute to corporate taxation.

Ftouhi, Ayed, and Zemzem (2016) reported that almost all companies prefer to pay lower taxes or get some tax savings on tax payable. Given that the main purpose of the company is more and more focused on minimizing the overall effective tax rate of the whole company or group in order to maximize its after-tax profits. Indeed, many tax-planning approaches have been used by company to achieve its objective. For example, tax deferral represents one of the basic tools of tax planning.

Tax planning techniques and mechanisms

Tax aggressive planning strategies has been noticed extensively by some well-known multinational enterprises (MNEs) including Apple, Starbucks, Google, Amazon, Halliburton and many others. They to shift their profits from high tax jurisdictions to low tax jurisdictions in other to minimize tax liabilities (Vella 2015). He listed some of the techniques and mechanisms from international taxation perspective as exploitation of transfer pricing rules; debt shifting; hybrid mismatch arrangements; tax treaty abuse; artificial avoidance of permanent establishment status and tax rulings.

Empirical review

The effect of tax planning on firms' value

Assidi, Aliani and Omri (2016) worked on the effect of tax optimization on firm's value of Tunisian companies for eleven years. The study used effective tax rate as a proxy to tax planning while the control variables are total accruals, total assets, change in property; debt; audit and sector of activity as independent variables on firm value. They used regression analysis to analyze the effect of tax planning on firm value. The results showed a negative effect of tax planning on firm value reporting meaning that managers were looking for smooth and loopholes in tax laws to minimize corporate tax and maximize their stakeholders' values.

Ftouhi, Ayed, and Zemzem, (2016) examined whether corporate tax planning behavior increases firm value of European countries. They used corporate effective tax rate and tax savings to measure tax planning while control variables are firm size, leverage, capital intensity, dividends, earnings management on firm value. They reported the impact of tax planning on firm value is a function of tax savings and effective tax rate in disclosures of tax reduction in the financial statements. They argues that tax planning affects negatively firm's value due to higher agency costs by analyzing a sample of 73 firms listed in the Euronext 100 index for the period from 2008 to 2012. The result show that the corporate effective tax rate are below the statutory tax rate of the listed firm meaning that tax taxpayers use tax planning to reduce tax liability in obtaining the tax saving benefits while expose to risk related to inspection or investigation by tax authorities.

Lestari1 and Wardhani (2015) worked on the effect of tax planning on firm value with moderating board diversity for non-banking and financial firms in Indonesia stock exchange form 2010 to 2011. They used tax planning as independent variable while control variables are age, minority, background study/education, book value equity, industry dummy, earnings management, leverage, capital intensity, board director size, pre book tax income on firm value as market value of equity. The result positive effect of tax planning on firm value meaning that Indonesia firms use tax planning polices to reduce their tax liability.

Ilaboya, Izevbekhai and Ohiokha (2016) worked on the review of literature of effect of tax planning and firm value. They articulated extant literature of tax planning on firm value with a view to identifying gaps for further extensive empirical consideration. They reported that companies are always looking for means to reduce their corporate tax liability, and this has led to some high-level corporate fraud involving tax evasion in both developed and developing countries. They identified gaps that require hardcore empirical investigation to reduce the inconsistencies observed in the results of the literature reviewed such as inconsistency in research findings, measuring tax planning and theory in explaining the issue of tax planning. The result shows tax planning is either illegal or unethical which will always have positive or negative effect on firms' value.

Nwaobia, Kwarbai, and Ogundajo, (2016) worked on the effect of tax planning on firm value using 50 consumer goods firms in Nigeria from 2010 to 2014. They used regression analysis on effective tax rate as proxy for tax planning while control variables are firm size, leverage, tangibility of assets, capital allowance, investment tax credit, re-investment allowance, firm age and dividend on firm value. The result show positive effect of tax planning on firm value meaning that only an optimal mix of tax planning strategies could yield optimal benefits in the area of firm value enhancement to manufacturing firms in Nigeria. That firms are expected to stimulate research into appropriate delineation of tax planning strategies into those that could positively influence firm value in the short

run and those that are better utilized for the purpose of cash flow enhancement, that would in the short run, improve capacity utilization and positively impact firm value in the long-run.

Kaworl and Kportorgbi (2014) worked on the effect of tax planning on firms' market performance using non-financial companies listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange over a twelve year. They adopted panel regression to analysis the effect of tax planning, sales growth, firm size, leverage and age on firm performance proxied as Tobin's q. Their result shows a significant position effect of tax planning and firm value meaning that firms' engage in intensive tax planning activities when tax authorities maintain low corporate income tax rates that have a neutral influence on performance of firms under the study.

Jacob and Schütt (2013) worked on the effect of tax planning on firm valuation using 2820 firms in United States excluding financial firms and investment trusts from 1975 to 2011. They decompose the Feltham and Ohlson (1995) and Ohlson (1995) valuation model into expected future tax rates and pre-tax numbers using ordinary least square regression analysis to analyzed the dependent and independent variables. Their result show positive significant effect of tax planning on firms valuation meaning that good (poor) tax management increases (decreases) the effect of pre-tax earnings on the market-to-book ratio

The effect of tax savings on firms' value

Ftouhi, Ayed, and Zemzem, (2016) examined whether corporate tax planning behavior increases firm value of European countries. They used regression analysis to analyze the effect of tax savings on firm value. They reported the impact of tax planning on firm value is a function of tax savings in disclosures of tax reduction in the financial statements. They argue that tax savings affects firms value negatively due to higher agency costs. The result show that the corporate effective tax rate are below the statutory tax rate of the listed firm meaning that tax taxpayers use tax saving policies to reduce tax liability in obtaining the tax saving benefits while expose to risk related to inspection or investigation by tax authorities.

Hafkenscheid and Janssen (2009) worked on the whether income tax savings policies creates firms value using content analysis of theories of tax planning. they argue that tax planning strategies do create company value, that the value created by tax saving should be calculated separately from the value created by growth of the operating profits. Their result shows that many investors and analysts said they disregard tax as a value driver because they lack the relevant information, that firms generally are reluctant to provide information on their tax position, often arguing that this would negatively affect their position toward the taxing authorities.

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The effect of effective tax rate on firms' value

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Ftouhi, Ayed, and Zemzem, (2016) examined whether corporate tax planning behavior increases firm value of European countries. They used effective tax rate as the total tax expense scaled by pre-tax accounting income as measure to tax planning. They argue that corporate effective tax rate assesses the tax performance of firms, as it summary statistic of tax performance which describes the amount of taxes paid by a company relative to its gross profit which reflects aggressive tax planning of a firm. The result show that the corporate effective tax rate has a negative significant effect on firm value meaning that tax taxpayers use tax saving policies to reduce tax liability in obtaining the tax saving benefits while expose to risk related to inspection or investigation by tax authorities.

Nwaobia, Kwarbai, and Ogundajo, (2016) worked on the effect of tax planning on firm value using 50 consumer goods firms in Nigeria from 2010 to 2014. They used regression analysis on effective tax rate as proxy for tax planning while control variables are firm size, leverage, tangibility of assets, capital allowance, investment tax credit, re-investment allowance, firm age and dividend on firm value. The result show positive effect of effective tax rate on firm value meaning that only an optimal mix of tax planning strategies could yield optimal benefits in the area of firm value enhancement to manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

The effect of book tax gap on firms value

Dwi , Yulianti and Debby (2011) worked on the book-tax gap in Indonesia listed firms 1999 to 2008. They used regression analysis to analyze the dependent and independent variables by analyzing the gap thoroughly, without restriction on the type of differences using the Indonesian tax law. The result show negative significant effect of the book tax gap on Indonesian value of firms meaning that tight supervision of the Indonesian tax authorities affects firms' valuation.

Plesko (2006) worked of the book tax differences and the measurement of corporate income. The result shows that while taxes are an important element in corporate decision-making, the determination of a firms tax liability is based on a separate set of rules than income reported to shareholders. Publicly available data appear to have limited ability to provide the necessary information to measure taxable income and evaluate the statutory burden of the corporate tax.

The effect of tax shelter on firms value

Ryan (2008) worked on the examination of corporate tax shelter participants using United States firms. The study examines the financial reporting effect of tax shelter participation on a sample of 59 firms accused by the government of engaging in tax shelter activity by developing of a model of tax shelter participation using the sample of identified tax shelter firms. The study analysis tax shelters by examining set of firms identified in tax court records and press articles as having participated in corporate tax shelters, which includes cases involving transfer pricing; corporate-owned life insurance transactions; contingent payment instalment sales; contested liability accelerations; ease-in, lease-out

deals; cross border dividend capture cases and two intellectual property havens. The result indicates that the difference in book tax differences between the tax shelter firms and the matched control firms is largely a function of the tax shelter activity, with tax sheltering having positive effect on firm size and the existence of foreign income. It also show that tax shelter firms with strong corporate governance exhibit significant positive abnormal returns during the period of active tax shelter participation which negatively affects the value of the firm.

Hanlon and Slemrod (2009) in Lee, Dobiyski and Minton (2015) worked on the theories and empirical proxies for corporate tax avoidance. They identify 108 tax sheltering cases for 97 firms from the Factiva Database during the period from 1990 to 2004, analyzing tax shelters by examining set of firms identified in tax court records and press articles as having participated in corporate tax shelters, which includes cases involving transfer pricing; corporate-owned life insurance transactions; contingent payment instalment sales; contested liability accelerations; ease-in, lease-out deals; cross border dividend capture cases and two intellectual property havens. They use the event study methodology to examine the market response to the press news of tax shelters. The results shows that investors show negative responses to tax shelters with a variation across the industry, for example, more negative reactions to corporations in the retail sector while less negative reactions to corporations with a high cash effective tax rate. These results can be interpreted that investors might be concerned about the potential relation from consumers for the image of unscrupulous corporate citizenship of corporations with tax shelters. However, investors are less concerned about the aggressive tax strategy for corporations with a high cash effective tax rate than those with a low cash effective tax rate.

Schallheim and Wells (2004) worked on whether firms really under-levered using more than 40,000 firm-year observations form the period of 1987 to 1999 of listed United States firms they used book tax differences, the difference between taxes paid and financial statement tax expense to evaluate tax shelter activities of the firms. They reported sources of tax spread as tax favored investing activities, timing differences, and permanent differences. Differences between financial and tax income revenue and expense recognition policy give rise to timing differences. These timing differences create deferred tax account balances that give rise to tax shelter. They used tobit regression analysis to analyzed the dependent and independent variables. Their result shows a positive significant effect of tax shelter on value of firms meaning that firms' uses tax spread as alternatives to debt to reduce taxable income and increase shareholder wealth.

McGill and Outslay 2004 worked on lost in translation: detecting tax shelter activity in financial statements of United States listed companies. They study tries to find out whether financial statements of public U.S. corporations provide sufficient information to the public to determine a corporation's tax payment to the U.S. Treasury and since involvement in "tax shelter" transactions has been much debated since the well-publicized collapses of Enron Corporation and WorldCom, Inc. They specify examples to demonstrate how "income tax note" data can be analyzed to answer these two questions and, in so doing, point out the limitations of using financial accounting information to address tax-related issues. The result show that financial statements have limited information to detect actual tax shelter while with suggestions to increase the transparency of a corporation's tax activities through enhanced disclosure.

In summary, most of these prior studies were done in developed countries such as United States and European countries, as well as in emerging economy as Tunisian, Indonesia, Ghana, Nigeria and others. All the previous studies used one tax planning variable with control variables as this study brings together all established tax planning variables to find out its effects on value of selected listed firms. This leave room for our empirical judgment in Nigeria listed firms, to see whether the result will be consistent with previous studies.

3.0 Methodology

Research design

The study is of an ex post facto design. We use secondary data by obtaining financial information covering selected trading listed companies from 2013 to 2015 according to their published financial statements. The reason for this selection is to determine the effect of tax planning on value of trading listed companies. The study covers different sectors ranging from agriculture, conglomerates, construction/ real estate, consumer goods, health care, ICT, industrial goods, oil and gas; and services. The combination of different sectors are to have a robust result on the effects of tax planning policies on the firm value of trading listed companies.

Population of the study

The population of this study is made of all the Nigeria companies that are categorized under Nigeria business environment. However, both quoted or not quoted in the Nigeria stock exchange market.

Sample size

The sample consists all 53 trading listed companies on the Nigeria stock exchange categorized under different sector ranging from agriculture, conglomerates, construction/ real estate, consumer goods, health care, ICT, industrial goods, oil and gas; and services, the total of 159 firm-year observations. It excluded financial companies such as banking, insurance and mortgage sectors. We create an unbalanced panel for 2013, 2014 and 2015 for all selected listed companies. The data are unbalanced due to some companies are consistent in some variables; some are not consistent; and some companies has incomplete year. Also, the selected companies was based on listed companies which listed daily share prices has traded consistently more than 10,000 units for the past one year in respect to volume of share trading. The reason are to capture the effect of their tax planning policies on value of the firms.

Estimation procedure

The assumption in panel data regression is that the dependent variable is a linear function of the independent variables with consideration to heterogeneity in the pooled selected trading listed companies. This means that pooled regression assumed that there is no difference in the pooled selected trading listed companies while panel regression assumed cross-section heterogeneity (cross section fixed effect) and period heterogeneity (time fixed effect).

Model Specification and Measurement of Variables

In specifying our panel regression model for the effects tax planning policies on firm value, our major variables are tax planning (TaxP); tax saving (TaxSav); effective tax rate (ETR); book tax gap (BTG);

and tax shelter (TaxShelter). Also included in the model are cross-section (selected trading listed companies) and years (2013 – 2015) in the panel regressions.

The panel regression with an error term (μ_i) for model 1 is expressed in equation (1)

$$\text{Tobin } q_{it} = f(\text{TaxP} + \text{TaxSav} + \text{ETR} + \text{BTG} + \text{TaxShelter}) \dots \text{equ (1)}$$

$$\text{Tobin } q_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{TaxP}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{TaxSav}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ETR}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{BTG}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{TaxShelter}_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \text{equ (2)}$$

$$\text{Tobin } q_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{TaxP}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{TaxSav}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ETR}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{BTG}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{TaxShelter}_{it} + \beta_6 \text{Modifi~l}_{it} + \beta_7 (\text{TaxP} * \text{Modifi~l})_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \text{equ (3)}$$

$\alpha_i = \text{constant}$

Dependent Variable

Tobin q_{it} = Tobin Q. It is the ratio between a physical asset's market value and its replacement value introduced first by Nicholas Kaldor in 1966 and reintroduce by James Tobin in 1968. It measures firm assets in relation to the firm's market value. We use a modified version of the Tobin q by Chung and Pruitt 1994 in Wolfe & Sauaia 2003 for consistency of their simplified balance sheets:

$$q = (\text{MVS} + \text{D})/\text{TA}$$

Where:

MVS = Market value of all outstanding shares, i.e. the firm's Stock Price * Outstanding shares; TA = Firm's assets, i.e. cash, receivables, inventory and plant book value; D = Debt defined as: $D = (\text{AVCL} - \text{AVCA}) + \text{AVLTD}$. AVCL = Accounting value of the firm's Current Liabilities = Short Term Debt + Taxes Payable. AVLTD = Accounting value of the firm's Long Term debt = Long Term Debt. AVCA = Accounting value of the firm's Current Assets = Cash + Inventories + Receivables Shares.

Independent Variables

TaxP_{it} = tax planning, following Lestari 1 and Wardhani 2015 tax planning is seen as leading to increase after tax earnings and therefore to be in the interest of shareholders, this is typically taken in valuation model/firm value (Desai and Dharmapala, 2009; Wahab and Holland, 2012; Desai and Dharmapala, 2006). It is computed as difference between the government statutory tax rate and the effective tax rate with pre book tax income ($\text{TaxP} = 30\% - \text{ETR} * \text{PBTI}$), where effective tax rate are corporate tax expense exclude deferred tax expense with pre book tax income ($\text{ETR} = \text{CTE}/\text{PBTI}$). The apriori sign is $\beta_1 > 0$

TaxSav_{it} = Tax Saving: following Khaoula, Amor and Ahmed 2014; Kawor and Kportorgbi 2014, tax saving is calculated as difference between the statutory tax rate and the effective tax rate ($\text{TaxSav} = 30\% - \text{ETR}$). Where a firm operates across a number of jurisdictions with varying statutory rates, tax rate differentials can provide a tax saving recognized in firm value. Ftouhi, Ayed and Zemzem, 2010 in Kawor and Kportorgbi 2014 reported that managers have incentives to reduce financial statement tax expense because, tax planning is considered as a mechanism through which firms generate permanent tax savings and/or temporary tax savings achieved through deferrals. The apriori sign is $\beta_2 > 0$

ETR_{it} = Effective Tax Rate: following Ftouhi, Ayed and Zemzem, 2016; Soufiene, Khaoula, and Mohamed 2016; Aliani, 2014; Dyreng, Hanlon, and Maydew, 2010; Wilson, 2009; Kawor and Kportorgbi 2014; Nwaobia, Kwarbai, & Ogundajo, 2016, effective tax rate is calculated as the total

tax expense scaled by pre-tax accounting income ($ETR = CTE/PBTI$). Corporate effective tax rate assesses the tax performance of firms. Thus, it is the best measure to evaluate the actual corporate tax burdens. Effective tax rate is a commonly used measure of a firm's tax burden, provides a basic summary statistic of tax performance, which describes the amount of taxes paid by a company relative to its gross profit. This measure reflects aggressive tax planning through permanent book-tax differences. The apriori sign is $\beta_3 < 0$.

BTG_{it} = Book Tax Gap: following Dwi, Yulianti and Debby 2011; Penman 2001; Desai and Dhamarpala 2009, Wang 2010, book tax gap is calculated as the difference between accounting income and taxable income ($BTG = EBIT - TPE$). Penman (2001) even stated that book-tax gap could be used as red flag to determine any cost manipulation, where higher book-tax gap is also considered as an indication of low quality financial statements. The apriori sign is $\beta_4 > 0$.

$TaxShelter_{it}$ = Tax Shelter: following Wilson 2008; Graham and Tucker 2006 in Lee, Dobiysanski, and Minton 2015, A tax shelter is any method taxpayers create to reduce their taxable income without valid business purposes. Graham and Tucker (2006) illustrate mechanics of tax shelters corporations that adopted to reduce taxable income, such as (1) lease-in lease out, (2) accelerated transfer of contested liability, (3) corporate-owned life insurance, (4) transfer pricing, (5) cross-border dividend capture, (6) contingent-payment installment sales, (7) liquidation and re-contribution, and (8) offshore intellectual property havens.

We used the above descriptions as tax shelter while we measure tax shelter according to Graham and Tucker 2006 in Lee, Dobiysanski, and Minton 2015 identifying sheltering corporations: (1) the dockets of Tax Courts and other courts for litigation in which public corporations were accused of a tax shelter and (2) the popular press that reported public corporations with a Notice of Deficiency from the Internal Revenue Service regarding tax shelters. we assign 1 to tax shelter corporations ,otherwise we assign 0. The apriori sign is $\beta_5 > 0$

Moderating variable

Modifi~l = Modified Jones model. We proxy earnings management with modified Jones model. The model estimates firms' abnormal accruals (discretionary) based on certain economic and accounting fundamentals using time series regression used by Dechow, Ge, and Schrand, (2010), Dechow, and Dichev (2002). $\mu_t = DA_t = \{TA_t\} - \{(\beta_{0i} (1/T_{t-1}) + \beta_{1i} (\Delta REV_t - \Delta REC_t) + \beta_{2i} (PPE_t))\}$ Where DA_t = Discretionary accruals in year t, TA_t = Actual total accruals from financial statement data = $\{\Delta \text{Current assets} - \Delta \text{cash} - \Delta \text{current liabilities} - \Delta \text{Current maturities of long-term debt} - \Delta \text{Income taxes payable} - \text{Depreciation and amortization expenses}\}$, ΔREV_t is the change in revenues from last year to this year, ΔREC_t is the change in receivables from last year to this year, PPE_t is the book value of property, plant and equipment. The model measure of the firm's operations before managers' manipulations. It is expected that total accruals, which includes changes in accounts receivables, rely on the extent of changes in revenue, as revenues are to control for firms economic environment, the gross property, plant and equipment control for the portion of total accruals related to non-discretionary depreciation expense. The prediction error in the model, μ_t measures the level of discretionary accruals.

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis of Results

In this study, we investigated the effect of tax planning policies on firm value of high volume trading companies on the Nigeria stock exchange. The study uses high volume trading companies ranging

from agriculture, conglomerates, construction/ real estate, consumer goods, health care, ICT, industrial goods, oil and gas; and services as sample according to their financial statements from 2013 to 2015. A sample of 53 high volume trading firms formed our sample with 159 observations; to ensure adequate observation for statistical testing, we adopted a panel data analysis to identify the possible effects on the firm value. To this end, we conducted descriptive statistics and correlation matrix. Pooled and panel regression with fixed and random effect panel data regression and the Hausman test were also conducted to select between fixed and random effect models.

Table 4.1
Descriptive Statistic of 53 trading listed companies in Nigeria on Firm value over three years period

Descriptive Statistic					
Variables	Mean	Max	Min	Std. Dev	JB (P-Value)
TobinQ	36.7352	2105.860	-0.6501	261.7898	17344.91 (0.00)*
TaxPlanning	2785544.	185,000,000	-63,447,365	20,077,112	17181.51 (0.00)*
TaxSaving	0.1010	0.817300	-18.3673	1.566089	93445.28 (0.00)*
ETR	0.3936	18.6673	-0.5173	1.5676	93017.95 (0.00)*
BTG	39,482,587	1,920,000,000	-102,000,000	219,000,000	18555.34 (0.00)*
TaxShelter	0.4716	1.0000	0.0000	0.5007	26.50(0.00)*
No of Cross-section	53				
All data observations	159				

Source: Authors' Computations.

NOTE *1% level of significance, ** 5% level of significance and ***10% level of significance

Table 4.1 from appendix two shows the mean (average) for each of the variable, their maximum values, minimum values, standard deviation and Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics (normality test). The results in table 4.1 provided some insight into the nature of the highly volume trading firms used in the study. Firstly, the large difference between the maximum and minimum values of Tobin Q shows that the highly volume trading firms have different firm value. Secondly, it has observed that on the average over the three years period (2013 – 2015), the sampled highly volume trading firms has 36.73 of Tobin q meaning that our sample have a position firm value. We also observed that Tobin q over the period was 2105.86 maximum while the minimum stood at -0.65. This shows that highly volume trading firms have different firm values. However, tax planning over the period was N185,000,000 maximum while the minimum stood at N-63,447,365. These wide variations in tax planning policies and firm values therefore justify the need for this study, as highly volume trading firms taxation polices affects their firm values differently. Our sample companies are heterogeneous due to panel data. The panel analysis accommodates times as well as the heterogeneity effect of the listed companies, which may be random or fixed

Lastly, in table 4.1, the Jarque-Bera (JB) which test for normality or the existence of outliers or extreme values among the variables are normally distributed at 1% level of significance. This means that any variables with outlier are not likely to distort our conclusion and are therefore reliable for drawing generalization.

Correlation Analysis

In examining the relationship among the variables, we employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) and the results are presented in table 4.2

Table 4.2

Correlation Matrix of 53 trading listed companies in Nigeria on Firm value over three years period

	TobinQ	TaxPlanning	TaxSaving	ETR	BTG	TaxShelter
TobinQ	1.0000					
TaxPlanning	-0.0173	1.0000				
TaxSaving	0.0191	0.0233	1.0000			
ETR	-0.0184	-0.0225	-0.9991	1.0000		
BTG	-0.0239	0.0910	0.0188	-0.0180	1.0000	
TaxShelter	0.1473	-0.1436	-0.0935	0.0956	-0.1535	1.0000

Source: Authors' Computations.

The use of correlation matrix in most regression analysis is to check for multicollinearity and to explore the association between the each explanatory variable and the dependent variable. Table 4.2 focuses on the correlation between firm value (Tobin q and share prices), tax planning policies (TaxPlanning, TaxSaving, ETR, BTG and TaxShelter).

The findings from the correlation matrix table, shows that there is a weak negative association between Tobin q (-0.00). This clearly shows that Tobin q represent firm assets in relation to the firm's market value, it justified that the use of the variables for our hypotheses testing. In the case of tax planning (TaxPlanning, TobinQ = -0.01,) we observed that, tax planning rate was negatively and strongly associated with TobinQ. This suggest to tax planning polices decrease the value of trading firms. Effective tax rate shows a negative strong association with TobinQ (-0.01) meaning high effective tax rate affects firms value while book tax gap shows a negative strong association with TobinQ (-0.02) as it indicate that large tax different on trading firms has a negative effects on their firm value. Tax shelter have a strong positive association with TobinQ (0.14) meaning that tax reduction increases the firm performance and value. In checking for multicollinearity, we notice that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This means that there is the absence of multicollinearity problem in our model. Multicollinearity between explanatory variables may result to wrong signs or implausible magnitudes, in the estimated model coefficients, and the bias of the standard errors of the coefficients.

Regression Results

However, to examine the effect on the dependent variables firm value and tax planning polices and to also test our formulated hypotheses, we used a panel data regression analysis since the data had both time series (2013 to 2015) and cross-sectional properties (53 high volume trading companies). The panel regression results are presented and discussed below.

Tobin Q

The Tobin Q panel regression results examine how tax planning policies and its interaction effect on firm value. The general hypotheses of this model one is that there is no significant effect of tax planning policies on firm value. The result obtained are presented in Table 4.3

Table 4.3 TobinQ panel regression result of 53 trading listed companies in Nigeria on Firm value over three years period

	Aprrior Sign	TobinQ (OLS Pooled)	TobinQ (Fixed Effect)	TobinQ (Random Effect)	TobinQ (Fixed Effect)
C		-8.77 (-0.08) [0.92]	36.67 (3.44) [0.00]*	0.30 (0.00) [0.99]	38.87 (3.28) [0.00]*
TaxPlan	+	3.68 (0.14) [0.88]	1.38 (0.04) [0.09]***	1.58 (0.04) [0.96]	5.24 (0.04) [0.96]
TaxSav	+	37.61 (0.11) [0.90]	0.44 (0.01) [0.09]***	0.56 (0.01) [0.98]	4.12 (0.10) [0.91]
ETR	+	32.08 (0.09) [0.92]	0.30 (0.00) [0.09]***	0.41 (0.01) [0.99]	1.28 (0.03) [0.97]
BTG	-	-3.28 (-0.14) [0.88]	-1.24 (-0.02) [0.09]***	-1.59 (-0.02) [0.97]	-1.56 (-0.02) [0.98]
Modifi~1	+				20.97 (0.51) [0.60]
TaxPlan * Modifi~1	+				-6.34 (-0.03) [0.97]
TaxSav * Modifi~1	+				-59.96 (-0.39) [0.69]
R-Squared		0.02	0.90	0.00	0.99
Adj-R-Squared		-0.00	0.90	-0.02	0.99
F-Statistic		0.72(0.60)	354.39 (0.00)*	0.21 (0.95)	321.04 (0.00)*
Hausman Test				0.18(0.09)***	1.99 (0.09)
N(n)		159(53)	159(53)	159(53)	144 (48)

Source: Author 2017

Note: (1) Parentheses () are t-statistic while bracket [] are p-values
 (2) * 1%, ** 5% and *** 10% level of significance

Discussion of Tobin Q regression results

In testing for the cause-effect between the dependent and independent variables in firm value (Tobin Q), we reported pooled and panel analysis. The study adopted the three widely used pooled and panel data regression models (fixed effect and panel data estimation techniques). The difference in these models is based on the assumptions made about the explanatory variables and cross sectional error

term. Since the results would be more appealing statistically in the context of different in our sampled companies

In table 4.3, we presented an OLS pooled regression and two panel data estimation techniques (fixed effect and panel data estimator). The three results revealed difference in their coefficients magnitude, signs and number of significant variables. This clearly shows that pooled OLS regression does not reflect the heterogeneity in the sampled companies. This effect is reflected in the two panel data regression results. In selecting from the two panel data models, the Hausman test was conducted and the result shows that we should accept H_0 (adopt fixed effect model and reject random effect model). This means that we adopt, interpret and draw policy recommendation from the fixed effect panel data regression results.

Following the above, we will therefore discuss the fixed effect panel regression result from Table 4.3. In Table 4.3, the R-squared and adjusted R-squared values were (0.99) and (0.99). This indicates that all independent variables jointly explain about 99% of the systematic variations in Tobin Q of our sampled companies over the three-year period (2013 – 2015). The above average R-squared value is realistic as it clearly shows firm value and its interaction with tax planning policies. The F-statistics (321.04) and its p-value (0.0) show that the firm value (Tobin Q) fixed effect regression model is generally significant and well specified. The F-statistic also shows that the overall firm value (Tobin Q) fixed effect regression model is significant at 1% levels. The impact of tax planning (*TaxPlan*), tax saving (*TaxSav*), and effective tax rate (*ETR*) on firm value is positive and statistically insignificant in model. It means that sampled trading companies use tax planning to reduce tax liability in obtaining the tax saving benefits to enhance firm value. With positive influence on firm value and also conform to apriori expectation. This finding like similar studies (Ftouhi, Ayed, and Zemzem, 2016, Lestari1 and Wardhani 2015, Ilaboya, Izevbekhai and Ohiokha 2016, Nwaobia, Kwarbai, and Ogundajo, 2016, Kawor1 and Kportorgbi 2014, Jacob and Schütt 2013) confirms that tax planning polices reduce tax liability which increases firm value while unethical tax planning expose firms to risk related to inspection or investigation by tax authorities. While the result regarding to the impact of book tax gap (*BTG*) on firm value is negative and statistically insignificant in model. This means that increase in book tax gap of trading companies reduce the firm value of sampled companies. This finding like similar study Dwi, Yulianti and Debby 2011 confirm that book tax gap negatively affect value of Indonesian firms due to tight supervision of the Indonesian tax authorities. The results indicate that modified jones model (Modifi~1) also positive and insignificantly moderate the relationship between earnings management and firm value. These results prove that the efficient earnings management will increase firm value. Meanwhile, the interaction of modified jones model (Modifi~1) as well as tax planning (*TaxPlan*) and tax saving (*TaxSav*) with tax planning exerts negative and insignificant effects on firm value. This implies that change in tax planning and tax savings leads to decrease in firm value.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

This study which is primarily motivated by the need to have better understanding of how the host tax planning influences firm value in presence of earnings management, investigates the theoretical relationship between tax planning and firm value in 53 quoted companies in Nigeria using unbalanced data covering 2013 -2015. The results from fixed panel analysis reveal a number of interesting new evidence which would undoubtedly bridge knowledge gap in the literature. In broader terms, this paper addresses two research questions among which is whether tax planning significantly impacts

firm value and if the adoption of earnings management influences the impact of firm value? Specifically, this study concludes that (1) tax planning insignificantly serves as an indicator on tax agency investigation and inspection; (2) the negative interaction of tax planning and earnings management implies that earnings management favourably moderates the connection between tax planning and firm value.

The findings of this study give rise to some important implications that worth noting by policy makers in Nigeria. First, empirical evidence that suggests positive insignificant impact of tax planning (*TaxPlan*), tax saving (*TaxSav*), and effective tax rate (*ETR*) on firm value; goes to demonstrate that the level of tax planning of sampled firms in Nigeria driven by the extent of the tax planning, tax saving, and effective tax rate, which reflects the tax planning while holding other factors constant. Consequently, sampled trading companies use tax planning to reduce tax liability in obtaining the tax saving benefits to enhance firm value. Secondly, the evidence showing that earnings management exerts positive and insignificant moderating impact on the relationship between tax planning and firm value in Nigeria. These results prove that the efficient earnings management will increase firm value. Meanwhile, the interaction of modified jones model (Modifi~1) as well as tax planning (*TaxPlan*) and tax saving (*TaxSav*) with tax planning exerts negative and insignificant effects on firm value. This implies that change in tax planning and tax savings leads to decrease in firm value. Therefore, the study recommends that firm should engage in ethical tax planning to affect firm value positively and maximize shareholders wealth, in other to avoid penalties from tax authorities that affects firm value negatively.

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